

SILK FIBRE COMPOSITES

Aart W. van Vuure*, Jan Vanderbeke*, Nedda El-Asmar**, Ignaas Verpoest*

*Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Department of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering,
Kasteelpark Arenberg 44, B-3001 Heverlee Belgium,

** Designer Silversmith, Elisabethlaan 162, B-2600 Antwerpen Belgium

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Abstract

The mechanical performance of silk fibre composites employing a range of matrix materials was assessed. A balanced twill weave fabric was chosen and matrices were selected on the basis of their strain to failure (toughness). Low velocity impact measurements show that the penetration energy is a strong function of matrix strain to failure. Apparently, in a tough matrix the silk fabric can shear and absorb a lot of energy; there is however also a significant extra contribution from the matrix. Tensile test results confirm that woven twill weave silk fibre composites show a strong increase in both strength and elongation to failure in the 45° direction, upon increasing the matrix strain to failure, demonstrating that silk fabric composites can be very tough when selecting the right, tough matrix.

1 Introduction

Natural fibre composites offer considerable advantages to the composite materials community, especially with respect to their environmental performance.

Natural fibres are renewable resources which means that they are largely CO₂ neutral. There is some effective amount of CO₂ emitted during their processing (due to energy consumption), but this quantity is much lower than the amount emitted during manufacture of synthetic fibres like glass and carbon fibre. Natural fibres are inherently biodegradable, which may be beneficial. They can be thermally recycled (in a CO₂ neutral way).

Due to their relatively low density, high specific mechanical properties are obtained, which can be comparable to glass fibre for some fibres like flax, hemp, kenaf and bamboo.

Other advantages are potential low cost (not for silk fibres) and relatively low investment needed for cultivation. Natural fibres are typically less

abrasive than glass or carbon, e.g. leading to lower wear in textile processing and to potentially lower occupational health risks due to fibre dust.

Potential drawbacks of natural fibres which need to be addressed are natural variability in properties (necessitating some overdesign), moisture sensitivity and insufficiently optimized adhesion with typical composite matrices.

This paper describes research on Bombyx Mori (cocoon) silk fibre composites. Silk fibres distinguish themselves from most other known reinforcing fibres by an exceptionally high strain to failure (18-20% for Bombyx Mori, even 28-30% for spider silk, compared to a few percent for glass and carbon fibre, and flax, hemp and bamboo fibre for that matter). It will be shown in this paper that this exceptionally high strain to failure can be translated into very tough composite materials with the choice of the right matrix material.

Silk fibre composite panels with a range of matrix polymers were prepared and both basic mechanical properties like stiffness and strength as well as low velocity penetration impact resistance were measured.

2 Materials and Methods

Silk fibres were provided by an undisclosed silk fibre manufacturer. For this study an untreated, balanced twill weave fabric was used of 80 g/m². The epoxy resin used was a novolac resin obtained from M.C. Technics and was processed into 0.3 mm thick resin infusion films. A range of thermoplastic films was obtained from various suppliers, in film thicknesses ranging from 30 to 120 μm. Different chemical compositions (with different levels of polarity) and a range of strain to failures were selected.

Epoxy composites were prepared in a press-clave set-up employing resin film infusion. Thermoplastic composites were prepared by compression moulding of stacks of silk fabric and

thermoplastic films in a hot press. This is schematically shown in figure 1.

Previous processing studies [1] showed that to obtain good, well impregnated panels, the minimum temperature in the press needs to be about 25 degrees C higher than the melting temperature of the matrix and a minimum pressure of around 15 bars needs to be used. In this respect, it should be noted that silk fibres start to degrade thermally above 150°C.

Fig. 1. Processing of silk fabrics with thermoplastic films in a hot press

Tensile tests were performed according to ASTM D-3039 on an Instron tensile testing machine. Falling weight impact tests were performed on an impact rig according to ISO 6603-2 (see figure 2). A hemispherical striker tip with radius 8 mm was employed. Samples were 105 x 105 mm and were clamped by a support ring of 80mm diameter. Results are reported as the impact energy needed for penetration, normalized to the thickness of the composite plate (order 1 mm thickness).

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Impact resistance

Figure 3 shows the absorbed impact energy upon penetration for a range of silk fibre composites, as a function of the elongation to failure of the matrix material. There is a very strong effect. In all cases roughly the same amount of balanced twill weave fabrics with areal weight of 80 g/m² was

used, resulting in composite plates with fibre volume fraction around 50% and plate thickness of around 0.7 mm. The absorbed impact energy for dry silk fabric is also indicated. In this case the same amount of fabrics was chosen, corresponding to a fibre volume fraction of 50% in air.

Fig. 2. Impact set-up used for low velocity penetration impact measurements.

It is apparent that when embedded in more brittle matrices, the silk fabric cannot reach its full potential. In polar epoxy, which can be hypothesized to bond well to presumably moderately polar silk, the impact energy absorption is poor, probably due to localization of damage. This effect is well known from impact performance of composites; it is typically better to have a poorer interface, to allow damage to spread over a larger surface. For hydrophobic PLA, the impact energy is similar to dry silk fabric. It was observed that the PLA was fragmented and separated from the silk. It is hypothesized that due to the poor bonding between hydrophobic PLA and more polar silk, or even due to incomplete impregnation, the PLA is not contributing to the impact energy absorption, but the silk fabric can still absorb the energy.

Fig. 3. Absorbed impact energy upon penetration, as a function of the strain to failure of the polymer matrix, for (balanced) twill weave fabric silk composites.

When using tougher matrices, the impact resistance can rise substantially above the level of dry silk fabric. The mechanism of this is still not fully understood, but it seems that there is an extra effect from the tough matrix, on top of or in conjunction with the energy which can be absorbed by the silk. It is hypothesized that in a tough matrix, the silk twill fabric can fully shear and thus absorb a lot of energy (see also tensile test data and discussion furtheron). There may also be an effect of matrix stiffness, but typically for polymers, modulus is inversely related to strain to failure, with all polymers more or less situated on the same line.

A range of tough matrices, including thermoplastic elastomers, was tested. Although not enough data are currently available on the polarity of the different matrices, as compared to the polarity of silk, so far no substantial effect by difference in adhesion or impregnation (wetting) could be observed. Possibly, for tough matrices, the effect of interfacial adhesion is less pronounced, as it was so apparent for the brittle matrices evaluated.

Figure 4 shows the impact resistance of silk twill fabric composite with a matrix of PBSa, as compared to various other composite materials. It is apparent, that the impact resistance of silk fabric composites is very high. Currently, research is ongoing on aramid fibre composites and composites based on ultra high molecular weight polyethylene

fibre (tradename Dyneema). It seems these fibres can only match silk, in case their interface and consequently their mechanical properties like static tensile strength are weakened. First data for these fibres, do show a substantial effect of interfacial adhesion and/or impregnation, even for tough matrices, with highest energy absorption for a weak interface.

Fig. 4. Specific impact energy at penetration (normalized to density) for various composite materials.

Table 1 Tensile properties for silk composites with various matrices; balanced twill weave fabric

Matrix	Matrix strain to failure (%)	Test direction (°)	Fibre volume fraction (%)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Tensile strain to failure (%)	Tensile energy to failure (J/cm ³)	Impact energy (J/mm)
Epoxy	3	0	40	6.2	115	4.1		
		45		3.6	72	4.0	0.7	
Polypropylene	300	0	46	6.2	166	8		
		45		1.9	68	29	10.6	15.5
PBS	700	0	50	4.7	146	14		
		45		1.8	152	39		32
PBSa	900	0	50	4.2	131	12		
		45		1.45	143	38	25.1	42
PTMAT	700	45	50	0.6	156	46	29.2	43
PE-EVA	750	45	50	0.7	137	47	19.2	42
TPU ether	550	45	50	0.4	145	42	23.9	34
LDPE	670	45	50	1.0	122	42	15	42
Copolyamide	400	45	50	1.5	181	46	44	24

3.2 Tensile properties

Table 1 gives an overview of the tensile properties measured for twill weave silk fabric composites with a range of matrix materials.

In the first place it can be stated that the tensile moduli of the composites in both the 0° and 45° directions are as expected, following predictions based on laminate plate theory, assuming a 0/90° lay-up (ignoring fabric crimp and assuming a silk modulus of 16 GPa) [1].

The tensile strength in the 0° direction matches largely with the strength of the silk fibres (600 MPa). Interestingly, the composite strain to failure in the 0° direction increases with matrix strain to failure (figure 5). This can be attributed to reduced cracking in the 90° direction caused by strain magnification in the matrix. So far, even for elastomeric matrices, the in literature quoted strain to failure of silk fibres (18-20%) has not been reached, which may be attributed to damage due to fibre-fibre contact when loading a woven fabric.

The tensile strength in the 45° direction is a function of the strain to failure of the matrix. Apparently, for tougher matrices, the silk fabric can shear when loaded in the 45° direction and thus reach very high strain to failure and strength. For tough matrices the silk composites become isotropic in strength! This is schematically shown in figure 6.

Fig. 5. Composite strain to failure as a function of matrix strain to failure for twill weave silk fibre composites.

It was earlier hypothesized that the shearing mechanism in the 45° direction also contributes to high impact energy absorption. Figure 7 shows the correlation between impact energy and the tensile failure energy in the 45° direction for a range of thermoplastic matrices evaluated.

Fig. 6. Schematic representation of tensile properties of balanced twill weave silk fibre composites, in case of a tough thermoplastic matrix.

Fig. 7. Penetration impact energy as a function of tensile failure energy in the 45° direction, for twill weave silk fibre composites with various thermoplastic matrices.

It appears that this correlation is not very good, with apparently some optimum at intermediate tensile energies. The correlation with matrix strain to failure is much better, see fig. 3. A matrix like LDPE with a low modulus (0.35 GPa), but high strain to failure (670%), gives a relatively low composite 45° tensile energy (15 J/cm³), but a high composite impact resistance (42 J/mm). A matrix like copolyamide with a relatively high modulus (value not available), but lower strain to failure (400%), gives a high composite 45° tensile energy (44 J/cm³), but a lower composite impact energy (24 J/mm). It seems the particular shape of the stress strain curve in the 45° direction plays an important role. Relatively low modulus polymers may allow the fabric to take up a lot of shear upon impact and if the strain to failure of the matrix is

high the system can absorb a lot of energy. The interface strength may also play a role. Further research is ongoing to further elucidate the mechanisms at play here.

4 Conclusions

Silk fibre composites can be very tough materials when the right, tough type of matrix is selected. Results were presented for balanced twill weave silk fabric composites. It is hypothesized that due to shear, woven silk fabric composites can absorb a lot of energy, when embedded in a tough matrix, but it was hypothesised that there is probably also an extra contribution from the matrix itself.

The importance of fabric shear is supported by tensile test results in the 45° direction. The strength and strain to failure of the composites increase strongly with the toughness (strain to failure) of the matrix.

Interestingly, (balanced) silk fabric composites become isotropic in strength when a tough matrix is employed.

Further research is conducted on the role of the textile geometry. Also, the thermoforming behaviour of the materials is assessed.

References

- [1] Van Vuure, A.W., Wolnik, K., Dupont, S., Vanderbeke, J., El-Asmar, N. and Verpoest, I., "Silk fibre composites". *Proceedings of SAMPE Europe 27th International Conference*, Paris, 6 p., 2006.